

ASSESSMENT OF THE INFLUENCE OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON SOLAR RADIATION USING A SIMPLE CLIMATE MODEL

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ABSTRACT

The zero-dimensional model was used to assess the influence of climate change on solar radiation in Minna – Nigeria. Ten years climatic data (1998 – 2007) obtained from the Meteorological Department, Federal Airport Authority, Minna; served as input in zero – dimensional equation and statistical analyses. Zero dimensional was used in computing the radiative equilibrium for each year. The result showed that the radiative equilibrium increases yearly with increase in temperature. The various statistical analyses showed that temperature is closely related to the radiative equilibrium of the area during the ten years period. The relationships between the parameters were also analysed using two statistical analyses – correlation and regression. It was observed that temperature is more significant to radiative equilibrium than other parameters which include relative humidity, wind speed, and solar radiation. However, a new simple climate model was developed relating temperature to radiative equilibrium.

KEYWORDS: Radiative equilibrium, climate change, solar radiation and temperature.

INTRODUCTION

Climate change refers to changes in climate that are attributed directly or indirectly to human activities that alter the composition of the global atmosphere and which is in addition to natural climate variability. In other words, this term refers to changes that are brought about by human activities (Miller and Edwards, 2001). In recent usage, however, the term “climate change” often refers to changes in modern climate especially in the context of environmental policy. Baxter (2008) referred to climate change as any long term significant change in the average weather that a given region experiences, average weather in this case may include average temperature, precipitation, wind patterns and relative humidity. It includes changes in the variability or average state of the atmosphere over durations ranging from decades to millions of years and these changes can be caused by dynamic processes on earth including external forces such as variations in sunlight intensity and more recently human activities (Baxter et.al..2008). Other factors which influence climate change include distance from the sea, ocean currents, direction of prevailing wind, relief, proximity to the equator among others. Non climatic factors such as the green house gas, volcanism plate tectonics and orbital variation also affects climate change. Climate change has continued through out the entire history of the earth. The field of paleoclimatology has provided information on climate change in the ancient past, supplementing modern observations of climate.

The earth absorbs radiation from the sun (which is the radiant energy emitted by the sun as a result of its nuclear fusion reactions) mainly at the surface. This energy is then redistributed by the atmospheric and oceanic circulations and reradiated back to space at longer wave length. The incoming solar radiation energy is balanced approximately by the out going terrestrial radiation. Any factor that alters the radiation received from the sun or lost to space or alters the redistribution of energy within the atmosphere, land and the ocean can affect climate (Svenson et.al.. 2005).

Any changes in the radiative balance the earth including those due to an increase in green house gases or in aerosols will alter the global hydrological cycle and atmospheric and oceanic circulation thereby, affecting weather patterns, regional temperatures and precipitation (Carr, 2008). Also any human induced changes in the climate will be embedded in the back ground of natural climate variations.

The climate model

Climate models use quantitative methods to simulate the interactions of the atmosphere, Oceans, land surface and ice. They are used for a variety of purpose from study of the dynamics of the weather and climates system for projections of future climate. Climate model are systems of differential equations based on the basic laws of physics, fluid motion and chemistry (Jacklyn, 2001).

Climate models balance or very nearly balance incoming energy as short wave electromagnetic radiation to the earth with out going energy as long wave electromagnetic radiation from the earth and any balance in a change in the average temperature of the earth. A very simple model of the radiative equilibrium of the earth is the zero – dimensional model which is written as:

$$(1 - a) S = 4\epsilon T^4$$

The left hand side represents the incoming energy from the sun and the right hand side represents the outgoing energy from the earth. This model determines the effect of the average earth temperature on changes in solar output or effective earth emissivity (Gilbert, 2008).

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The objectives of this study are to predict the influence of climate change on solar radiation using a simple climate model. The specific objectives are:

- i. To evaluate the influence of climate change using a simple climate model.
- ii. To analyse the variability in solar radiation during the period of study.
- iii. To develop a model suitable for Nigeria climatic conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was carried out in Minna, Niger State. Minna lies within the Southern Guinea Savanna zone of Nigeria, with a mean annual rain-fall of about 1,200mm. The temperature rarely falls below 22°C while wet season temperature average about 28°C. The peak temperature is 40°C in the month of March.

DATA SOURCE

Climatic data were obtained from the Meteorological Department, Federal Airport Authority, Minna. Ten years of daily data (1998 – 2007) were used. The climatic data available at the station include, temperature (minimum and maximum), relative humidity, wind speed and solar radiation. Data collection was done by FAAN trained staff. Weather instruments installation conformed to world meteorological organization (W.M.O.) standards.

ANALYSIS OF THE DATA

An empirical formula was used in computing the radiative equilibrium. The climatic data (daily, monthly and annual) were analyzed using correlation and regression analysis .

The mean annual temperatures were determined by summing up the mean monthly temperature and dividing by the number of months per year. The annual solar radiation data for the ten years period were calculated by summing up the monthly solar radiation and dividing by the number of months per year.

Determination of the radiative equilibrium.

The radiative equilibrium is an equilibrium between the amount of radiation leaving the earth's surface. Monthly and annual radiative equilibrium were determined using a simple climate model which is zero dimensional model.

The model is written as

$$(1 - a)S = 4\epsilon T^4 \text{ (J}^\circ\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}\text{)}$$

Where; a = the earth's average albedo measured to be 0.3.

S = Solar constant which is about 1,367m⁻²

€ = the effective emissivity of the earth which is 0.612

σ = Stefan Boltzman's constant; which is approximately $(5.67 \times 10^{-8} \text{ J}^0\text{m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1})$.
 T = monthly / annual temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)

The results of the analysis are presented in tables and graphs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1.0 shows the annual mean temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity, and wind speed. It also, shows the annual radiative equilibrium for the ten years period spanning 1998 - 2007 which was calculated using zero dimension equation.

Table 1.0: Annual temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity, wind speed and relative equilibrium for ten years (1998 – 2007).

Years	Annual temp. $^{\circ}\text{C}$	Solar radiation (m/s)	Relative humidity (%)	Wind speed (km/hr)	Relative equilibrium ($\text{J}^0\text{cm}^{-1}\text{s}$)
1998	26.7	11.3	50.1	93.1	0.07
1999	28.0	8.8	52.8	77.4	0.09
2000	29.2	6.0	51.6	99.1	0.10
2001	30.4	6.5	50.5	113.64	0.12
2002	31.4	7.1	50.1	97.1	0.13
2003	31.6	6.7	51.2	94.7	0.14
2004	31.9	6.7	51.2	94.7	0.14
2005	32.1	7.1	50.7	88.9	0.15
2006	32.5	7.4	52.3	79.1	0.16
2007	32.9	7.6	52.3	83.2	0.16

Annual radiative equilibrium: The mean annual relatively equilibrium during the period of study is $0.126 \text{ J}^0\text{Cm}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. The lowest ($0.07 \text{ J}^0\text{Cm}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) and the highest ($0.16 \text{ J}^0\text{Cm}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) relative equilibrium were recorded in 1998 and 2006 / 2007 respectively. This is shown in Fig 1.0. when the annual relative equilibrium was plotted against the annual temperature; the graph is shown on Fig. 2.0.

When these parameters are correlated with each other, the result is as shown in Table 2.0.

Table 2.0: The correlated analysis of the various climatic data with relative equilibrium

Relative equilibrium	Temperature	Solar radiation	Relative humidity
1.000	0.990	-0.585	0.233
0.990	1.000	0.169	-0.130
-0.585	0.169	1.000	-0.325
0.233	-0.130	-0.325	1.000
-0.233			

A correlation factor of 0.990 and P of 0.000 in the correlation between temperature and radiative equilibrium indicates a high positive correlation between the variables. It also shows that this correlation is highly significant which means that the temperature has a marked effect on the earth's radiative equilibrium. This is also shown in Figs 1 – 3 which is in conformity with Svenson *et al.* (2005). From Figs 1, 2 and 3, it is clear that as the years go by the annual temperature increases and this led to an increase in the radiative equilibrium of the earth thus making the climate warmer (Gilbert, 2008).

A correlation factor of -0.585 with a P > 0.05 which was obtained from correlating solar radiation and radiative equilibrium indicates a strong, negative correlation between the variables and also shows that the correlation is significant. This is shown in Fig 1. where the graph implies that the solar radiation has negative effect on the earth's radiative equilibrium since the total amount of radiation from the sun is constant and calculated to be 956.9 using the

zero-dimensional model (Gilbert, 2008). Fig. 4 shows that the solar radiation decreased sharply from 1998 to 2000 and then increased slightly over the years.

Table 1.0 shows that the humidity increased sharply from 1998 – 1999 and fell to its lowest in 2002 and resulted into fluctuations from 2002 to 2007. This indicates a less effect on the radiative equilibrium of the earth. It is further explained in the correlation between the two variables with correlation factor of 0.233 and the P = 0.517 which signifies a low positive correlation and not highly significant. In other words humidity has no relationship with the earth’s radiative equilibrium. Correlation between wind speed and radiative equilibrium is not significant. There is a very weak negative correlation of -0.233, P = 0.535.

REGRESSION

Simple regression analysis was carried out, to observe the relationship between relative equilibrium and the various climatic data. The results of the analyses are presented in Table3 .0.

Table 3.0: Regression or relative equilibrium against various climatic data

Relative equilibrium	Temperature	Solar radiation	Relative humidity	Wind speed
R ²	98.1%	34.3%	5.4%	5.0%
P	0.000	0.075	0.517	0.532
F – cal	407.92	4.17	0.46	0.42
	P<0.05	P>0.05	P>0.05	P>0.05

From the regression analysis only temperature with a high R² value and a high F-cal value shows that the regression fits the data while in other parameters, regression analysis does not fit the data. Table 3.0 shows that relative equilibrium depends so much on temperature. As the temperature increases relative equilibrium also increases. This can be seen with the high value of R² (98.1%) and F-cal value of 467.92. The high R² value measures the amount of variation in the relative equilibrium that is accounted for by temperature. This means that regression fits the data and also implies that temperature can be used to predict changes in the earth’s radiative equilibrium. This increase in the relative equilibrium is noticed by the increased brightness of the sun due to increase in the global temperature (Ahlenius, 2007). This increase in brightness results to an increased solar radiation from the sun and thus increased terrestrial radiation from the earth resulting in an increase in the earth’s radiative equilibrium. From the regression analysis, the relationship between radiative equilibrium and temperature is given as $(1-a)s = -0.324 + 0.0147 \text{ Temperature}$.

The regression involving solar radiation and radiative equilibrium gives a low R² value which is 34.3% and F-cal value of 4.17. Similarly, in the analysis of regression involving relative humidity and relative equilibrium there is low R² value of 5.4% and a very low F-cal value of 0.46. The result is also not different for the regression of wind versus radiative equilibrium where the R² value is 5.0% which is the lowest and F-cal is 0.42. The regression of the above parameters are considered not to befit for the data and thus, can not be used to predict the earth’s radiative equilibrium, the result is clearly shown in Table 3.0.

CONCLUSION

The zero-dimensional model can be used to assess past and predict future radiative equilibrium of the earth. From the results obtained, temperature is the main climate factor influencing solar radiation and the increase in temperature has led to an increase in the radiative equilibrium thus increasing the amount of terrestrial solar radiation than from the earth did this has caused increased warming during the ten years of study. Other climatic factors have little or no influence on the earth’s radiative equilibrium.

This research work shows that the climate condition of a particular place can be monitored, predicted or assessed or using a simple climate model the zero-dimensional model, rather than using various climate parameters, instrument and data. However, a new simple climate model is developed for predicting radiative equilibrium. $0.324 + (1-a)s = 0.0147T$. It can be written as $(1-a)s = -0.324 + 0.0147T$ where T = temperature (°C).

It can be concluded that the knowledge of future temperature can be used to determine future radiative of equilibrium of the earth since increase in temperature is synonymous to the increase in radiative equilibrium.

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Fig 1: Graph of radiative equilibrium against years

Fig 2: Graph of radiative equilibrium against annual mean temperature

Fig 3: Graph of annual mean temperature against years

Fig 4: Graph of annual solar radiation against years

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